

4 - Metacognitive Strategy Instruction for Listening Comprehension: A Quasi-experimental Study in Kampung Inggris Pare, Indonesia

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Abstract

This quasi-experimental study investigated the effects of metacognitive strategy instruction on listening comprehension skills of 60 EFL learners enrolled in a TOEFL preparation program. The participants at a language institution in Kampung Inggris Pare, Indonesia's largest English learning area offering an intensive English immersion-based approach, were divided into experimental and control groups. The participants in the experimental group received a ten-session intervention program based on the Metacognitive Pedagogical Cycle. In contrast, the control group received conventional listening instruction following the syllabus provided by the institution. The data were collected through a standardized listening comprehension test from the TOEFL ITP® (Test of English as a Foreign Language – Institutional Testing Program) in both groups before and after the intervention program. The statistical analysis of the test scores shows that the results did not reveal a significant difference between the listening scores from the pre-and post-tests of the experimental group. However, the experimental group's mean scores in listening outperformed the control group, demonstrating a significant improvement after the treatment. These findings suggest potential benefits of metacognitive strategy instruction, though further research with larger sample sizes and extended interventions is recommended.

Keywords: metacognition, metacognitive strategy instruction, listening strategies, TOEFL

1. Introduction

Kampung Inggris, or English Village, located in the Pare Subdistrict of Kediri Regency, East Java, is Indonesia's largest immersion-based English language learning center. Established in 1977 with a single course, Kampung Inggris Pare (KIP) has since grown to include over a hundred English courses, attracting students from all over Indonesia (Mubarok et al., 2020). The initiative was started by Kalend Osen, founder of the Basic English Course (BEC), whose success inspired the creation of numerous other courses in the area, many of which were founded by BEC graduates. KIP provides an ideal environment for learning and practicing English, facilitated by English-speaking locals and students. Its rapid expansion reflects Indonesia's rising demand for English proficiency, fueled by the language's critical role in global communication and academic advancement. Students often attend KIP not only to improve their English but also to prepare for widely recognized proficiency tests, such as the Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL), which serves as a benchmark for academic and professional qualifications in Indonesia.

TOEFL preparation courses at Kampung Inggris Pare (KIP) are a popular choice for students preparing for various purposes, including graduation requirements, scholarship applications, job interviews, and institution-specific assessments. These courses are particularly attractive due to their relatively low cost and the widespread availability of official testing facilities across the country. Of the three primary skills taught in these courses—listening, structure, and reading—listening skills often receive less attention. Many English courses, including the Mahesa Institute, place a greater emphasis on grammar or structure. For instance, as an authorized test center for TOEFL ITP at KIP, the Mahesa Institute allocates 150-minute sessions for structure instruction, compared to only 90 minutes each

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for listening and reading (Mahesa Institute, 2023). This disparity results in insufficient listening practice, leaving students at a disadvantage in this critical skill area. Since early 2024, the average TOEFL ITP® listening scores at the Mahesa Institute have consistently been among the lowest, with CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) ratings indicating a B1 level in listening. By contrast, some students achieve B2 levels in the other sections, highlighting the gap in listening proficiency.

The listening section is often overlooked in language practice and curricula over extended periods (Field, 2008; Goh & Vandergrift, 2021; Luo & Gao, 2012). Yet, listening comprehension is widely acknowledged as a complex process that relies on both linguistic competencies—such as phonetics, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, and discourse analysis—and strategic or non-linguistic knowledge, including world knowledge (Buck, 2001; Vandergrift & Baker, 2015). To address these challenges, some students employ self-regulated learning strategies, among which metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI) has emerged as a promising approach. MSI enables learners to take control of their learning processes, fostering self-regulation and improving listening comprehension (Kobayashi, 2018). Research indicates that MSI activates learners' thinking and enhances their performance, especially for those struggling with listening (Anderson, 2022).

Prior studies have underscored the benefits of metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI) for less-skilled listeners (Bozorgian, 2012; Vandergrift & Tafaghodtari, 2010), highlighting its potential to improve listening comprehension across various proficiency levels. Moreover, MSI encourages teachers to reevaluate their approaches to listening instruction and equips learners to navigate the complexities of listening, enhancing both their performance and understanding (Goh, 2008; Vandergrift, 2004). While numerous studies have demonstrated the efficacy of MSI (Bozorgian, 2012, 2014; Maftoon & Fakhri Alamdari, 2020; Becker, 2020; Pei & Suwanthep, 2021; Robillos & Bustos, 2022; Singh et al., 2022), some have reported no statistically significant improvements (Liu, 2020; Rahimi & Maral, 2013). Despite these findings, studies reporting no significant differences still observed higher mean scores post-intervention, indicating potential benefits of MSI. The variability in results may be attributed to factors such as the intervention's duration and the nature of listening tasks employed (Bozorgian, 2014; Liu, 2020; Robillos & Bustos, 2022).

This study distinguishes itself from previous research in several significant ways. First, it specifically targets intermediate English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners who are native Indonesian speakers, setting it apart from studies focused on learners of other languages, such as Chinese (Liu, 2020), French (Becker, 2020), Persian (Bozorgian, 2012; Maftoon & Fakhri Alamdari, 2020), or Thai (Robillos & Bustos, 2022). Second, it utilizes the TOEFL ITP® listening test for assessment, yielding findings that are directly relevant to students preparing for this widely recognized standardized exam. This contrasts with prior studies employing alternative materials, such as IELTS listening tests (Bozorgian, 2012), video-based tests (Robillos & Bustos, 2022), or proprietary assessment tools (Maftoon & Fakhri Alamdari, 2020). Additionally, this study's intervention spans 10 sessions, a longer duration compared to the 4- or 8-session interventions in some earlier research (Robillos & Bustos, 2022; Bozorgian, 2012). These distinctive aspects aim to offer deeper insights into the effectiveness of metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI), particularly within the context of TOEFL preparation for Indonesian EFL learners.

To achieve consistent and reliable findings and address gaps in the existing literature on the efficacy of metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI), this study investigates the effectiveness of MSI in enhancing listening comprehension skills. A quasi-experimental design will be utilized, with participants assigned to either an experimental group receiving MSI-integrated instruction or a control group following traditional listening instruction. Data will be collected from a quantitative perspective using pre- and post-test listening comprehension assessments. The findings are expected to contribute to a deeper understanding of MSI's impact on TOEFL listening preparation and provide valuable insights for English language instructors, particularly in intensive learning environments such as Kampung Inggris Pare (KIP). Additionally, this study aims to inform the development of effective TOEFL preparation strategies that integrate MSI to enhance students' listening skills and exam performance.

To address the objectives of this study, the following research questions are explored: **(RQ1):** Is there a significant difference in listening comprehension scores between EFL learners in a control

group and those receiving MSI in the experimental group? **(RQ2):** Does MSI help EFL learners improve listening comprehension?

In relation to the first research question, the following hypotheses were formulated: **(H₀)** There is no significant difference in listening comprehension scores between EFL learners in a control group and those receiving metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI) in the experimental group. **(H₁)** There is a significant difference in listening comprehension scores between EFL learners in a control group and those receiving metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI) in the experimental group.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Metacognition

Introduced by Flavell (1976), metacognition refers to the conscious utilization of cognitive strategies to achieve learning objectives, encompassing three key stages: activating a person's knowledge of cognitive processes related to the learning task, monitoring, and regulating these processes. In other words, metacognition involves the conscious ability to select, plan, evaluate, and revise cognitive aims, strategies, and goals. According to Flavell (1979), systematic instruction in metacognitive strategies can effectively enhance learners' metacognitive knowledge and skills. Wenden (1987) was the first to implement the concept of metacognition in second-language learning and teaching, introducing a taxonomy of metacognitive language and skills that has significantly influenced subsequent research on second-language acquisition. Goh and Vandergrift (2021) define metacognition as the ability to reflect upon and assess one's cognitive processes, including how information is processed and managed for various purposes. Building upon Flavell's (1979) conceptualization, they developed a metacognitive framework specifically for second-language learners, emphasizing three fundamental components: **metacognitive experience**, **metacognitive knowledge**, and **metacognitive strategies**, which collectively represent the core elements of metacognitive awareness. (1) The **metacognitive experience** involves the self-reflective thoughts and emotions an individual experiences while performing a task. It includes an awareness of one's cognitive processes. For example, in the context of listening, metacognitive experience may occur when a learner realizes their inability to identify a particular word but recalls overcoming a similar challenge in the past (Goh & Vandergrift, 2021). (2) Metacognitive knowledge is composed of three key elements: (a) **Person Knowledge**: Awareness of one's own learning characteristics, strengths, and beliefs about factors that contribute to success or challenges. (b) **Task Knowledge**: Understanding the goals, structures, and requirements of specific tasks. For listening, this includes recognizing discourse features, grammatical structures, and phonological aspects of connected speech. (c) **Strategy Knowledge**: Awareness of strategies that can effectively address learning objectives, enabling learners to select and adapt methods to achieve their goals. (3) **Metacognitive strategies** refer to the ability to apply specific, effective methods to enhance learning efficiency, enjoyment, and self-regulation. This involves knowing when and how to apply particular strategies based on strategic knowledge and awareness. Unlike metacognitive experience, which is more automatic, metacognitive knowledge and strategies can be explicitly taught and developed. All three components form a comprehensive framework that equips learners to become more self-regulated and adaptable, improving their learning efficiency and success.

2.2 Metacognitive Strategy Instruction (MSI) in Listening

Goh and Vandergrift (2021) define metacognitive strategy instruction as pedagogical procedures aimed at increasing learners' awareness of their listening processes. This involves expanding learners' metacognitive knowledge regarding their listening abilities, the inherent complexities and challenges of listening tasks, and the strategies available to enhance listening skills. Through metacognitive instruction, learners become more adept at employing key processes such as planning for the activity, monitoring comprehension, addressing comprehension challenges, and evaluating both their approach and outcomes (see Table 1).

Table 1 - L2 Listening Instruction through metacognitive processes (Goh & Vandergrift, 2021)

Metacognitive strategy	Instruction (for learners)
(1) Planning for the activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Activate prior knowledge related to the topic and any cultural insights that might support understanding ● Examine the text genre and remember possible structures or organization of information ● Predict specific vocabulary or ideas that are likely to appear in the listening material ● Anticipate the listening input based on the existing knowledge and relevant contextual information ● Prepare optimal listening circumstances by focusing attention and minimizing distraction
(2) Monitoring comprehension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Continuously evaluate understanding ● Compare understanding with real-world knowledge and verify coherence within the internal consistency ● Confirm predictions and acknowledge that it is unnecessary to comprehend each word ● Evaluate the learners' level of understanding ● Monitor learners' progress in understanding targeted information and important details ● Determine the effectiveness of the approach to text comprehension
(3) Solving comprehension problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adjust the strategies by implementing more suitable strategies as needed ● Making inferences by deducing the meaning of unclear parts by using context from understood sections ● Ask questions or seek additional context if the situation allows
(4) Evaluating the approach and outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reflect on challenges by identifying difficulties encountered during listening and analyze the reasons for these difficulties to improve future listening strategies ● Verify understanding with transcripts to confirm accuracy ● Evaluate the effectiveness of inferences and other strategies used.

Goh and Vandergrift (2021) propose that individuals adopt different methods of listening comprehension, influenced by factors such as information gathering and preparedness. Metacognitive knowledge about second language (L2) listening and prior knowledge also significantly impact this process. When listeners encounter difficulties or recognize incorrect predictions, they may revise their plans and employ problem-solving strategies to monitor and enhance comprehension. As task difficulty increases, listeners might revert to their original plans. The degree to which this process is automatic or consciously controlled depends on the listener's proficiency level: proficient listeners manage this process naturally, while those with lower proficiency require greater focus and deliberate effort. The metacognitive pedagogical sequence, initially developed by Vandergrift (2004, 2007) and later refined by Vandergrift and Goh (2012), aims to transform learners into self-regulating listeners by enhancing their awareness of the listening process. This approach provides learners with knowledge about themselves as listeners, the complexities of L2 listening tasks, and effective strategies. The overarching goal is to improve listening comprehension and foster success in L2 listening. The metacognitive process for active listening and comprehension is structured into sequential stages: **Planning and Predictions:** Learners predict content based on contextual clues and set expectations for focused listening. **First Verification and Planning:** Learners listen to evaluate their initial predictions and collaborate with peers to refine their strategies. **Second Verification and Comprehension Activity:** Learners engage in a second listening session, comparing predictions with actual input to construct a deeper understanding/ **Final Verification:** Learners listen again, often with a transcript, to confirm understanding while focusing on monitoring comprehension and solving problems. **Reflection and Goal Setting:** Learners evaluate their comprehension, identify strengths and weaknesses, and set future goals, fostering continuous improvement in listening skills. This structured approach helps learners develop greater self-awareness, enabling them to better manage the complexities of L2 listening and improve overall comprehension.

2.3 Previous Research on Metacognitive Instruction

Research on Metacognitive Strategy Instruction (MSI) for listening comprehension has predominantly been conducted in higher education settings. The duration of interventions varied from 15 to over 50 hours, spanning one to ten weeks, and employed diverse instructional approaches. Milliner and Dimoski (2021) implemented a combination of bottom-up and top-down strategies for Japanese university EFL learners, using textbooks and diaries across 50 instructional hours. Zeng and

Goh (2018) focused on college students in China, incorporating a self-regulated learning portfolio (SRLP) that included listening journals and monitoring forms. Liu (2020) employed a metacognitive learning cycle with training modules over six weeks for students in an intensive language program in the United States. Rezai et al. (2023) conducted 16 one-hour sessions twice weekly in Iran using a task-sequence or metacognitive process-based approach, though the specific materials used were not disclosed. In New Zealand, Madarbakus-Ring (2024) utilized TED Talk-based listening lessons and journal assessment sessions, featuring five 75-minute sessions with journal assignments and paper-based lessons. Other interventions included MSI in Oman, where Vellanki et al. (2022) used coursebooks and online platforms such as Moodle and Book-widgits. Similarly, Singh et al. (2022) implemented a four-week program for secondary students in Malaysia, featuring metacognitive instruction, lesson plans, and listening modules. Becker (2020) employed an assessment checklist to guide metacognitive strategy training, while Pei and Suwanthep (2021) integrated listening websites, online listening practice, and task resources for 39 low-proficiency Chinese university EFL students.

Various tools have been employed to evaluate listening comprehension after MSI interventions. Quantitative studies with intervention or experimental designs often utilized standardized language proficiency tests, with the most frequently administered tests being the International English Language Testing Service (IELTS) (Madarbakus-Ring, 2024; Mary et al., 2021; Vellanki et al., 2022), the Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC®) (Milliner & Dimoski, 2021), and the Oxford Quick Placement Test (OQPT) (Wang & Treffers-Daller, 2017; Pešić, 2022). Additionally, self-developed listening tests were commonly used, such as those by Becker (2020), Chon and Shin (2019), and Singh et al. (2022). Some self-developed tests were institution-specific, including the Malaysian University English Test (MUET) Listening Test and the L2 Listening Proficiency Test developed by the Seoul-Dongbu District Office of Education. These tests were typically administered before and after interventions and occasionally during the program.

The implementation of MSI for listening comprehension among EFL learners has received mixed reactions, with both advocates and critics. Research highlights numerous benefits of MSI, including significant enhancements in listening performance and self-regulatory abilities. MSI promotes active management of listening processes through structured strategies like planning, predicting, monitoring, and evaluating, fostering personalized learning and self-awareness in listening skills (Bozorgian et al., 2022; Wang & Treffers-Daller, 2017). It also encourages deeper engagement with listening tasks, reducing anxiety and boosting confidence (Bozorgian et al., 2022; Liu, 2020). Furthermore, MSI has shown the potential to develop automaticity in L2 listening processes, as demonstrated with L2 French learners (Becker, 2020), and provides distinct advantages for low-proficiency EFL learners, enhancing their comprehension and fostering confidence in listening tasks (Milliner & Dimoski, 2021). MSI is also valuable for scaffolding listening instruction and addressing teaching challenges, particularly in remote learning contexts (Vellanki et al., 2022).

However, some learners find MSI overly time-consuming, particularly when their focus is narrowly on intensive listening for exams (Zeng & Goh, 2018). This perception often stems from the reflective and structured nature of MSI activities, which may not align with learners prioritizing immediate results over skill development. Moreover, MSI's effectiveness can vary across foreign language classrooms, as its benefits are influenced by individual differences, such as learning styles, age, and proficiency levels (Cross, 2011).

3. Methodology

The researcher employs a quantitative approach, as it is well-suited for converting data into numerical forms, figures, and graphs and processing it using statistical procedures to establish differences or relationships between variables (Rasinger, 2013). Additionally, quantitative research enables precise measurement and analysis, hypothesis testing, and a deeper understanding of relationships between variables (Plonsky, 2015). Since this study examines the significant effect of metacognitive strategy instruction on TOEFL listening performance between two groups, a quasi-experimental research design is deemed appropriate. A quasi-experimental research design aims to determine whether changes in one variable directly cause changes in another (Rogers & Révész, 2019). This study was conducted in two separate classes: the control group class and the experimental group,

which received the intervention. The primary difference between the groups was the manipulated variable: explicit metacognitive strategy instruction.

3.1 Participants of the Study

Sixty participants, aged 18-24, were recruited from TOEFL preparation classes conducted between March and April 2024 at Mahesa Institute Pare, an authorized TOEFL ITP test center appointed by the Indonesian International Education Foundation (IIEF, 2024) in Kampung Inggris Pare (KIP). All participants were native Indonesian speakers, primarily university students, selected from the same language institute to ensure sample homogeneity. The participants were randomly divided into two groups: an experimental group (N=30) and a control group (N=30). The limited sample size was chosen due to several considerations. First, the research had a constrained timeline of approximately six months, making longitudinal interventions impractical. Second, the selected institution's regulations permitted small-scale classes with a minimum of five and a maximum of 20 students per class. Moreover, the small-scale design ensured that each participant in the experimental group received sufficient treatment. This study also served as a pilot, offering initial findings and refining the methodology for potential application in future large-scale studies. Both groups were taught by the same instructor, who held a bachelor's degree in English education, had over five years of teaching experience, and demonstrated advanced English proficiency with an ITP TOEFL score exceeding 600. The instructor received specialized training in delivering metacognitive instruction for the experimental group.

3.2 Instruments

The present study utilized the TOEFL ITP practice test, a standardized listening assessment published by ETS (Educational Testing Service), to measure listening performance. Two tests, used as pre-test and post-test, were designed to be equivalent in difficulty, each comprising 50 questions: 30 based on short dialogues and 20 on longer conversations and talks. Participants demonstrated their comprehension by answering multiple-choice questions with four answer options. These items assessed the ability to identify main ideas and details of academic and non-academic texts, infer meaning from speaker intonation, interpret idiomatic expressions, and understand the discourse functions of a text (Educational Testing Service, 2023). Correct responses were totaled to calculate listening performance, with one point assigned per correct answer.

3.3 Procedure

The researcher invited an English language institute and learners to participate in the study. Following institutional regulations and obtaining participants' consent, the teacher was contacted first to collaborate on providing explicit materials on metacognitive strategies for the experimental class. To maintain consistency, the same instructor taught both groups. After aligning on the strategies, agreements were reached regarding their application and the optimal time to deliver them to students. To avoid bias, the researcher did not participate in class activities. Both groups followed the regular course program outlined in the syllabus prepared by the institutions. The syllabus, structured for 20 meetings, emphasized practices and discussions. Each session started with material presentation, continued with listening activities, and concluded with corrections and discussions. The first five meetings focused on Part A (short dialogues), followed by Part B (extended conversations) and Part C (talks) in the next five meetings. The experimental group underwent a 10-session intervention program following the pedagogical cycles of Goh & Vandergrift (2021). Explicit instructions were provided after class for 30-45 minutes per session. The pedagogical cycle incorporated five stages emphasizing metacognitive strategies: 1) planning/predicting, 2) first verification, 3) second verification, 4) final verification, and 5) reflection (see Table 2). These stages corresponded to three main strategies: planning, monitoring, and evaluation (Goh & Vandergrift, 2021). During week one, learners practiced all five stages with instructor guidance. From week two,

they applied the stages independently and engaged in daily self-monitoring under supervision. Details of the metacognitive intervention program are presented in Appendix 1.

Table 2 - Stages in Listening Instruction through metacognitive processes (Vandergrift & Goh, 2012)

Pedagogical Stages	Metacognitive Processes
Pre-listening: Planning/predicting stage 1. After learners have been informed of the topic and text type, they anticipate the kinds of information and possible words they may hear.	1. Planning and directed attention
First listen: First verification stage 2. Learners verify their initial hypotheses, adjust them as required, and note any new information understood.	2. Selective attention, monitoring, and evaluation
3. Learners compare their understanding and notes with peers, modify as required, establish what still needs resolution, and decide on the important details that still require special attention.	3. Monitoring, evaluation, planning, and selective attention
Second listen: Second verification stage 4. Learners verify points of earlier disagreement, correct errors, and note additional details they understand.	4. Selective attention, monitoring, evaluation, and problem solving
5. Class discussion in which all members contribute to reconstructing the main points and crucial details of the text, interspersed with reflections on how learners arrived at the meaning of certain words.	5. Monitoring, evaluation, and problem solving
Third listen: Final verification stage 6. Learners listen specifically for the information revealed in the class discussion that they were previously unable to understand.	6. Selective attention, monitoring, and problem solving
Reflection stage 7. Based on the earlier discussion of strategies used to compensate for what was not understood, learners set goals for the next listening activity.	7. Evaluation and planning

3.4 Data analysis

The data analysis was conducted using Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. Descriptive statistics were first employed to summarize the pre-test and post-test scores of both the control and the experimental groups, presenting a general overview of the listening comprehension results. To ensure the appropriateness of parametric tests, the normality of the data was assessed using both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and Shapiro-Wilk tests, confirming that the data distribution fulfilled the necessary assumptions. Levene's test was then performed to verify the homogeneity of variances between the groups. An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups, examining the effect of metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI). To further evaluate the improvement of listening comprehension within the experimental group, a paired sample t-test was conducted to determine whether there was a significant improvement in listening comprehension after the intervention. Effect sizes, calculated using Cohen's *d*, provided additional insight into the practical significance of the findings, emphasizing the overall impact of MSI on listening comprehension.

3.5 Results

Before answering the first research question of whether metacognitive strategy instruction significantly affects the learners' listening comprehension score, this study covers the descriptive statistics and conducts normality tests as the initial steps. The results of the normality test will determine whether parametric or non-parametric tests are more appropriate for further analysis. **Table 3** reveals that on the pre-test, the control group had an observed mean score of $M = 432.67$ ($SD = 44.716$), while the experimental group, which received MSI, had a slightly higher mean score of $M = 458.00$ ($SD = 53.330$). on the post-test, the control group's mean score increased to $M = 469.00$ ($SD = 44.361$) while the experimental group's mean score improved further to $M = 487.00$ ($SD = 53.637$). The experimental group demonstrated a higher mean score on post-test scores after the intervention compared to the control group. The results highlight the potential positive effect of MSI, though further inferential analysis is needed to determine the significant statistical difference. **Table 4** presents the results of the normality tests for both the control and experimental groups through

the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. For the control group, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results are as follows; the pre-test statistics ($S = .139, p = .141$) and post-test statistics ($S = .134, p = .177$). Both p -values are greater than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the data distribution from the control group is normal. Similarly, for the experimental group, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test delivers the pre-test statistics test ($S = .141, p = .133$) and post-test statistics ($S = .155, p = .200$). Yet once more, the p -values surpass the significance level of 0.05, suggesting that the distribution of scores for both tests is normal. In addition, the results of the Shapiro-Wilk test also show that both the experimental and control groups distribute a normal distribution of data. The experimental pre-test ($S = .961, p = .323$), and experimental post-test ($S = .970, p = .536$) demonstrate p -values greater than 0.05. Moreover, the control group reveals pre-test ($S = .943, p = .106$) and post-test ($S = .957, p = .261$) which also confirm the normality of the data. Therefore, this satisfies the requirement for doing further parametric analyses. **Table 5** presents Levene’s test results, which specifically examine the assumption of equal variances between the control and experimental groups. The results ($p > 0.05$) indicate that the variances between these two groups are homogenous. **Table 6** presents the results of the independent sample test conducted to verify that the pre-test scores between the control and the experimental groups were equivalent before the intervention. The test results show that Sig. (2-tailed) = 0.051, which is slightly greater than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that there was no statistically significant difference between the pre-test scores of the control and the experimental group. Therefore, it can be concluded that both groups had statistically similar levels of listening comprehension before the intervention began. **Table 7** presents the results of an independent samples t-test conducted to compare the post-test scores between the control and experimental groups. The significance value (Sig. 2-tailed = 0.162) is greater than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the difference between the post-test scores of the control group and the experimental group is not statistically significant. The results answer the first research question that the learners who received MSI did not show a significantly higher improvement in listening comprehension compared to those in the control group. Finally, to assess the impact of the intervention within the experimental group, a paired samples t-test was conducted to compare pre-test and post-test scores. Results (Sig. 2-tailed value = 0.001), presented in **Table 8**, revealed that the control group exhibited a statistically significant difference between their pre-test and post-test scores ($p < .05$). While the intervention did not show a significant difference in score changes between the experimental and control groups, the participants in the experimental group demonstrated a significant improvement in their listening scores from pre-test to post-test.

Table 3 - Descriptive statistics: Analysis of pre-test and post-test

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pre-test (Control group)	30	432.67	44.716
Post-test (Control group)	30	469.00	44.361
Pre-test (Experimental group)	30	458.00	53.330
Post-test (Experimental group)	30	487.00	53.637
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 4 - Test of normality for listening comprehension test

Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Pre-test (Control group)	.139	30	.141	.943	30	.106
Post-test (Control group)	.134	30	.177	.957	30	.261
Pre-test (Experimental group)	.141	30	.133	.961	30	.323
Post-test (Experimental group)	.115	30	.200	.970	30	.536

Table 5 - Test of Homogeneity of variances between control and experimental groups

	Sign.
Pre-Test (Control group)	0.454
Pre-Test (Experimental group)	0.510

Table 6 - Equality of variance of pre-test scores between the control and the experimental groups

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
							Lower	Upper	
.570	.454	-1.994	58	.051	-25.333	12.707	-50.768	.102	
		-1.994	56.289	.051	-25.333	12.707	-50.785	.118	

Table 7 - Difference between post-test scores of the control and experimental groups

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
							Lower	Upper	
.440	.510	-1.416	58	.162	-18.000	12.708	-43.438	7.438	
		-1.416	56.028	.162	-18.000	12.708	-43.457	7.457	

Table 8 - Difference between pre-test and post-test scores after the intervention.

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Control group (pre- and post-test)	-29.000	41.219	7.525	-44.391	-13.609	-3.854	29	.001

4. Conclusions

The present study was conducted to investigate the potential of metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI) to enhance listening performance among ESL learners in *Kampung Inggris Pare* (KIP) by comparing the performance of a control group and an experimental group. The initial results of the pre-test show that the groups statistically demonstrated a similar level of listening comprehension before the intervention. The equivalence was confirmed by the independent t-test value ($p = 0.051$) which is greater than 0.05. Focusing on the first research question as to whether metacognitive strategy instruction through a structured pedagogical cycle (Goh & Vandergrift, 2021) consists of planning, verification, and reflection demonstrated a greater mean score in the experimental group compared to the post-test score in the control group. However, the independent t-test indicated that the difference in post-test scores was not statistically significant ($p = 0.162$). Therefore, the intervention of MSI did not result in a significantly greater improvement in listening comprehension for the experimental group compared to the control group.

A paired sample t-test conducted to assess the effect of the intervention within the experimental group showed that metacognitive strategy instruction (MSI) can help EFL learners improve listening comprehension (Sig. 2-tailed value = 0.001). These findings were in line with the previous studies (Liu, 2020; Rahimi & Maral, 2013). These studies also did not show any significant improvement after participating in MSI, but the higher mean scores observed in the experimental groups indicate a potential positive change that should be explored further. Furthermore, the effectiveness of metacognitive strategy instruction relied on several key factors, including active instructor involvement throughout the intervention and sufficient time given in the intervention program (Bozorgian, Fallahpour, et al., 2022; Liu, 2020).

The limitations of the study were the small number of participants as well as the limited time given in the intervention sessions. Since the research study is being conducted at a language institution, it was quite challenging to find a large group of EFL students with diverse levels of English proficiency to participate in this study on metacognitive strategy instruction in listening. Additionally, the researcher was unable to extend the duration of the intervention program due to the institution's

regulations. As a result, future research directions are required to include larger samples, learners with varied proficiency levels, and multiple educational settings.

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Appendix: Metacognitive intervention in the experimental class during 10 meetings, numbered 1 to 10 below:

Focus	Metacognitive Strategies/Activities
1 Listen to confusing sounds	Watched a video on metacognition to introduce the concept; held a Q&A session to clarify understanding; encouraged students to reflect on their prior self-learning experiences related to listening.
2 Idiomatic expressions	Guided students in setting self-learning plans based on metacognitive exercises; provided audio materials with transcripts for listening practice outside class; evaluated progress in subsequent meetings.
3 Functional expressions ([Dis]agreement, Suggestion, invitation, assumption)	Focused on monitoring comprehension and solving problems during listening tasks; facilitated class discussions to share strategies and findings; recommended additional practice at home with a focus on functional expressions.
4 Inference	Encouraged students to evaluate their own performance and strategies; introduced a unique learning strategy focusing on understanding the conversation context rather than immediately identifying correct answers.
5 Special verbs (causative verbs and 'used to')	Discussed challenges faced during strategy application; asked students to document unfamiliar vocabulary; guided them to use these reflections for targeted listening practice.
6 Extended conversations: 'Cross country skiing' and 'spelunking'	Introduced extended conversations with unfamiliar topics; asked students to predict content and brainstorm based on context before listening; facilitated discussions to confirm predictions and identify new information.
7 Extended conversations: 'Swallow bird' and 'campus self-tour'	Focused on prediction and contextual guessing for topics students found unfamiliar; encouraged peer discussions to share understanding and progress; monitored their ability to apply strategies independently.
8 Talk: 'New use of bacteria' and 'Dormitory cafeteria'	Reinforced the process of prediction and contextual understanding for longer talks; guided students to focus on key information and unfamiliar words, using contextual clues to infer meaning.
9 Talk: 'Nocturnal animal' and 'The ecology of coral reefs'	Encouraged self-monitoring during listening; asked students to reflect on new vocabulary and concepts; emphasized using context to understand the meaning in extended talks.
10 Weekly test	Evaluated students' progress through reflection activities; focused on three subcategories: performance evaluation, strategy evaluation, and problem identification; emphasized using reflections to set future goals and improve listening skills.